

Investigating submerged prehistoric settlements of Lake Ohrid, Albania: Transferring knowledge from UNESCO world heritage sites of the Alpine Space to Southeastern Europe – Report on the Lin 3 field season of 2024

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1. Introduction

Ongoing research in 2018–2024 within the interdisciplinary archaeological/bioarchaeological ERC Synergy Grant project “Exploring the dynamics and causes of prehistoric land use change in the cradle of European farming” (EXPLO) demonstrated that the lake region in the borderland zone of Albania, Greece and Northern Macedonia in the southwestern Balkans offers an exceptional potential for investigating Europe’s prehistoric lakeside settlements (fig. 1). Numerous archaeological wetland sites across Albania, Greece and North Macedonia were discovered, investigated, and systematically analysed (BALLMER, HAFNER & TINNER 2025; BOLLIGER et al. 2023; BRECHBÜHL et al. 2023; BRUNNER et al. 2025; HAFNER et al. 2021; KOTSAKIS & GIAGKOULIS 2025; MACZKOWSKI et al. 2021, 2025; MACZKOWSKI, BOLLIGER & FRANCUZ 2024; NAUMOV et al. 2019; REICH et al. 2021, 2025; YERMOKHIN et al. 2025a).

Neolithic, Bronze Age and Iron Age submerged settlements of the Alpine region have been the focus of intensive archaeological investigations for more than 170 years and were labelled as a serial transborder UNESCO cultural world heritage site in 2011 (HAFNER 2014, 2020). Switzerland has developed significant expertise in the archaeology of waterlogged sites, in underwater archaeology and in applying dendrochronology for high-precision dating of sites. Due to a wave of infrastructure measures (high-ways, buildings, railway projects) starting in the 1970s, numerous modern large scale rescue excavations went on for more than three decades. Since the 1980s dendrochronology is a standard absolute dating method in alpine lake dwellings with more than 100 000 wood samples processed (HAFNER 2024; MANNING 2023; TEGEL et al. 2022). However, the state of research and the development of an effective cultural heritage management in Albania remains rudimentary compared to the Alpine area (MENOTTI & O’SULLIVAN 2012).

Fig. 1 Location of Lake Ohrid and prehistoric wetland archaeological sites in the border regions of Albania, Greece, and North Macedonia. Sites with available dendrochronological data are indicated by green dots, and Lin 3 is labelled in red (map: A. Maczkowski, University of Bern, EXPLO project)

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The site of Lin 3, community of Pogradec, on the western shore of Lake Ohrid, Albania, is identified as the oldest pile-dwelling settlement of Europe and keeps an important role for the emergence of agriculture on the European continent. Research from the years 2021–2023 proved in Lin 3 the existence of several settlement phases between 6000 and 4000 BCE. The 2024 excavation campaign has significantly advanced our understanding of the various phases of Lin 3 especially towards the topics of chronological setting, settlement development, architectural practices and societal behaviour. The 2024 excavation campaign was conducted from 22 June to 20 August, as a collaborative effort between the National Institute of Archaeology, Academy of Sciences of Albania – represented by Adrian Anastasi and Ilirjan Gjipali – and the University of Bern under the lead of Albert Hafner, Martin Hinz and Mirco Brunner. Students and volunteer divers from Albania, Colombia, France, Germany, Kosovo, Poland, Switzerland, the United Kingdom and the United States participated in the fieldwork and were trained in wetland and underwater archaeology, digital measurement and documentation technologies and fulfilled multiple tasks in the excavations. The 2024 research support of the Swiss-Liechtenstein Foundation for Archaeological Research Abroad (SLSA) aimed to bridge a gap in the funding of the last phase of the ERC Synergy grant project EXPLO, which was substantially affected in the starting phase by the Covid-19 pandemic.

Fig.2 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Neolithic lake shore settlements, 6000–4000 BCE,
location of the site on the western shore
of Lake Ohrid, view in direction to the eastern
shore, North Macedonia (photo N. Linke,
University of Bern, EXPLO project)

2. Field work in Lin 3, Lake Ohrid

2.1 Surveys and excavations 2020–2023

The prehistoric lakeside settlement of Lin 3, located to the south of the prominent peninsula on the western shore of Lake Ohrid in Albania, represents one of the most extraordinary archaeological discoveries in Europe of recent years (figs. 2 and 3). The first reports from underwater archaeological research at the site were published in 1984 (CEKA & ZEKO 1984). As part of the national project “*Underwater Archaeological Map of the Albanian Coast*”, the Institute of Archaeology in Tirana discovered five more pile-dwelling sites on Lake Ohrid when returning to the Lin 3 site in 2005 (ANASTASI 2014, p. 478–479). As part of the ERC EXPLO project, systematic sections were made for the first time and sample material was recovered for dendrochronological and archaeobotanical investigations. As the oldest known pile-dwelling site on the continent, Lin 3 offers a unique window into early agrarian societies, wetland adaptation strategies, and community organization. Its remarkable preservation of wooden structures, artefacts, and environmental contexts provides unprecedented opportunities to study early farming societies in a dynamic landscape shaped by fluctuating water levels.

Fig. 3 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Neolithic lake shore settlements, 6000–4000 BCE,
location of the trenches 2021–2024 (map
M. Hinz, University of Bern, EXPLO project)

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Terrestrial excavations in 2022 and 2023 took place on the northern part of the site. These trenches near the shoreline yielded exceptionally well-preserved cultural layers including wooden piles, pottery, grinding stones, and burned clay deposits, all clear indicators of settlement remains. Stratigraphic analysis suggested a single-phase occupation around 5800 BCE. Underwater archaeological field work in 2021 and 2023 focused on the eastern part of the settlement area marked by wooden piles. The trenches of 2021 provided evidence of settlement phases around 5200, 4500 and 3900 BCE. Within the trenches of 2023 two palisade systems from the period 4500–4000 BCE were discovered.

2.2 Terrestrial excavation trench T9000 (2024)

The work of 2024 in the terrestrial part of the Lin 3 site focused on 24 m² trench T9000 (fig. 4). The decision to extend the excavations in this area was driven by the need to clarify the settlement stratigraphy and assess the preservation conditions of archaeological remains, particularly in relation to findings from the adjacent trench T6000 of 2023. Here a dense concentration of structural remains, including wooden piles, was found. The primary objectives for 2024 were to deepen trench T9000 to the natural, sterile lake marl, to refine the stratigraphic relationship between terrestrial and lacustrine deposits, and to enhance the site's chronological framework through additional sampling of wood (figs. 5–8).

Building on the clear stratigraphy established in trench T6000 of 2023, and corroborated by sediment-core data, we could confidently predict the depth at which archaeological horizons would appear. To expose archaeological layers efficiently while preserving fragile remains, the excavation began with the removal of upper, sterile lake sediments using a mechanical excavator. Each exposed surface was documented through a combination of photogrammetry, using handheld and drone-mounted cameras, sketching, and detailed written descriptions of soil composition, colour changes, and the presence of archaeological features. GIS-based recording was employed to accurately map all significant features and finds within the trench. Excavation proceeded in controlled spits of approximately 10–20 cm, with each newly exposed planum being documented before further removal of sediment. Water management remained a crucial aspect of the excavation process, as groundwater intrusion posed a significant challenge. A drainage trench was created around the excavation area to channel water into a designated drainage pit, which facilitated controlled groundwater removal. Profile stability was another major concern, particularly given the instable nature of trench walls. To prevent disruptions and ensure

Lin III, Piles

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the safety of the excavation team, profile protection sheeting was installed, mitigating risks and preventing delays caused by trench edges.

A systematic sampling strategy was implemented to maximize the recovery of environmental and archaeological material. All newly identified wooden piles were carefully sampled and tagged with the projects numbering system. Soil samples were collected from all excavation quadrants for archaeobotanical investigations, adhering to strict contamination prevention protocols. All excavated material was processed through wet sieving to ensure the recovery of small finds. Special attention was given to potential concentrations of burnt clay, charcoal, and pottery clusters, as these could indicate structural remains or activity areas within the settlement. More than 300 kg of sediments were shipped from Albania to Oxford university laboratories. Upon completion of the excavation, trench T9000 was covered with geotextile, followed by manual backfilling of a protective sediment layer before the trench was completely refilled using a mechanical excavator.

Post-excavation processing followed established protocols to ensure comprehensive documentation and preservation of finds. All artefacts were recorded on-site, with the more significant ones measured, photographed, and all carefully packed for storage and further analysis. A total of 37 674 artefacts with a combined weight of 191.5 kg were recovered from trench T9000 during the 2024 excavation season, representing a wide range of archaeological materials. The most abundant category by both count and weight was animal bone, with 17 274 fragments (59.0 kg), followed by ceramic sherds, which accounted for 16 895 pieces (84.3 kg). Lithic artefacts made from flint (silex) were less numerous but still significant, with 1807 pieces weighing approximately 3.1 kg. A notable portion of the assemblage comprised of potential remains from heating or oven installations (burnt clay with polished surface, BCPS), totalling 1850 fragments and 20.6 kg, while stone tools and fragments were relatively rare, with just 28 pieces but a notably high combined weight of 22.9 kg, due to the presence of heavier objects such as querns.

Fig. 4 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania Trenches 4000 (2022), 6000 (2023) and 9000 (2024) in the terrestrial part of the site, and wooden piles with label numbers (graphics M. Müller, University of Bern, EXPLO project)

Fig. 5 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Terrestrial excavation of 2024, trench 9000,
overview of the excavation site (photo M. Hinz,
University of Bern, EXPLO project)

Fig. 6 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Trench 9000, working situation, view to the south
(photo M. Hinz, University of Bern, EXPLO
project)

Fig. 7–8 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Trench 9000, working situation with piles
and ceramics in the lower parts of the trench,
near to bottom line (photos M. Hinz, University
of Bern, EXPLO project)

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Material distribution varied substantially by stratigraphic unit. The highest count of objects was recorded in Spit 7 (21 758 items), largely due to a concentration of ceramic and bone fragments, whereas Spit 8, though lower in count (6367 items), yielded the highest cumulative weight (81.8 kg), primarily due to dense ceramic clusters and heavy stone artefacts (querns). Spit 5 also yielded a large and diverse assemblage (6232 finds, 62.5 kg), with all major material classes represented, including the only instance of substantial stone tool recovery (14 items, 15.8 kg). These distributions reflect stratigraphic variation in activity zones and depositional processes and correspond well to the two main occupational phases identified in the trench stratigraphy.

Post-excavation analysis is being conducted by a team of specialists: Ilir Gjipali and Adrian Anastasi (Institute of Archaeology, Tirana) is responsible for the ceramic material, Rudenc Ruka (Institute of Archaeology, Tirana) for lithic artefacts, and the Oxford archaeobotanical team led by Amy Bogaard is analysing the faunal remains. All material was recorded, cleaned, and prepared for specialist analysis according to standardized project protocols.

2.3 Underwater excavation fields 6 and 7 (2024)

In the lacustrine (lake-side) part of the site (figs. 2 and 3), the excavation areas labelled as Fields 4 and 5 in 2023 were extended further eastward in 2024, resulting in the creation of new excavation sectors designated as Fields 6 and 7. The purpose of this expansion was to enlarge the investigated area to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the clearly visible palisade structures and the anticipated remains of buildings, as well as to clarify the situation along the outer edge of the settlement zone. The 2024 underwater excavations followed established protocols, employing a combination of diver-assisted excavation, and photogrammetry (figs. 9 and 10). To record the site with high precision, a GIS-based mapping approach was used alongside single-image photogrammetry, a simplified version of Structure-from-Motion (SfM) that had already proven effective in earlier campaigns. The systematic underwater sampling of wooden piles, mostly pines and oaks, provides an extensive dataset for dendrochronological analysis.

Altogether, an area of 400 m² within the lake was systematically documented during 2023/2024. Excavations at the settlement's periphery revealed that the organic cultural layers, once certainly present and preserved, have now largely eroded. The finds recovered from this zone – particularly durable materials such as stone artifacts, pottery fragments, and even a copper chisel – were discovered without any clear stratigraphic context,

Fig. 9 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Setting of the underwater excavation of 2024, fields 6 and 7. The black Zodiac boat serves as the base on site. The red Zodiac boat is used for shuttling divers and material to the land base. Pumps are installed on the boat on the left. Water hoses are leading to the diving area in the centre, where three divers are visible. The motor pump system creates an artificial current providing good visibility for the archaeologists at work in a depth of 2 m. (Photo M. Lehmann, University of Bern, EXPLO project)

Fig. 10 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Underwater excavation of 2024, working
situation (photo M. Lehmann, University
of Bern, EXPLO project)

scattered across loose sandy deposits interspersed with numerous wooden piles. This situation is strikingly similar to that observed in many lakeside settlements in the Alpine region, where erosion has also extensively affected those portions of settlements situated further out in the lake. The absence of intact cultural layers allows for relatively rapid excavation progress and the exposure of larger structural features. The principal objective of this work is to determine the extent of the settlement area in this direction, to document the palisade systems encountered, to identify possible house layout plans, and to assess the overall preservation state of the site with regard to ongoing erosion processes.

3. Results

3.1 Terrestrial excavation trench T9000 (2024)

The excavation in trench T9000 largely confirmed the findings from trench T6000 (2023), revealing further evidence of a settlement structure with material remains indicative of a domestic occupation (ceramic, silex, querns, burnt clay), including architectural elements consistent with building construction. However, significant finds and well-defined features allowed for a considerable refinement and expansion of previous results, particularly in terms of settlement stratigraphy, ceramic typology, and structural organization.

The excavation and detailed profile analysis revealed two distinct stratigraphic horizons in trench T9000, in contrast to the single stratigraphic layer observed in trench T6000. As in the previous excavation, a peat layer was present on top of the sequence, but notably, the two settlement phases below this layer were clearly differentiated. These horizons were particularly evident in the ceramic assemblages: while ceramic with impressed patterns had been entirely absent in the upper layers of trench T9000, as well as in trench T6000 from the 2023 excavation, it was clearly represented in the lower settlement phase of trench T9000. This suggests an earlier ceramic tradition associated with this deeper occupational layer, pointing to a longer and more complex habitation sequence than previously recognized. Further typological differences were preliminarily noted in the field and await more detailed analysis.

A significant structural distinction was also observed in the wooden piles, where two distinct erosion levels could be identified, each corresponding to one of the two settlement phases. The identification of two discrete building phases represents a major advancement in understanding the temporal development of the settlement. Meanwhile, this has also been substantiated by dendrochronological analysis.

Within the lower settlement layer, an exceptionally dense concentration of ceramic finds was recorded in the northern section of the trench (fig. 7). These deposits were concentrated around areas containing burnt and smoothed clay, which are tentatively interpreted as collapsed hearths or ovens. Further to mention are several “special vessels,” which were found intact and with preserved contents. Among the other significant finds, a complete flint blade measuring approximately 25 cm in length stands out due to its remarkable size (fig. 11). Additional broken fragments suggest that this was not an isolated occurrence, raising questions about production techniques and raw material procurement. Furthermore, a double-conical barrel-shaped *Spondylus* bead with a diameter of approximately 3 cm was recovered, along with multiple fragments of anthropomorphic figurines. These finds contribute valuable new data to discussions of personal adornment, symbolic objects, and craft traditions within the settlement. A particularly notable discovery was the identification of human remains, marking the first time that such finds have been associated with the site. Three cranial fragments were recovered, which, based on preliminary in-field assessment, are likely to represent at least two individuals.

The results from trench T9000 provide new insights into the spatial and chronological development of the settlement at Lin 3, further refining previous interpretations and adding complexity to the understanding of its occupation history. The presence of two clearly distinguishable settlement phases, separated by a sterile lake deposit, suggests that the site was not continuously occupied but rather settled in at least two distinct construction events (fig. 12). This episodic pattern of habitation aligns with broader regional trends in wetland settlement, where environmental fluctuations, resource availability, or social factors may have influenced periods of abandonment and reoccupation.

The presence of wooden piles in both settlement phases confirms that constructions using a wooden frame was the predominant architectural strategy at the site. However, the identification of two distinct erosion levels associated with these piles suggests that variations in water levels or sedimentation processes played a crucial role in shaping the preservation conditions of architectural elements, as well as the general settlement history of the site. In addition to these indicators of domestic occupation, traces of burning observed on some of the piles introduce the possibility that at least one of the architectural units was destroyed by fire. This hypothesis is supported by the spatial association between ceramics, burnt clay, and structural remains. The fact that these fire installations were found in a collapsed state is particularly revealing, as it confirms that the houses were raised structures. This aligns with the broader character of the site, where a sharp distinction between cultural layers and lake sediments indicates that occupation took place above standing water. The findings thus reinforce the interpretation of Lin 3 as a pile-dwelling settlement, with its structures elevated above fluctuating water levels, likely adapting to seasonal or long-term environmental changes.

The discovery of impressed ceramic ware (exclusively) in the lower settlement phase represents a significant chronological and cultural marker, distinguishing this earlier occupation from the subsequent phase. The complete absence of this ceramic style in trench T6000 of 2023 suggests a deliberate shift in ceramic traditions over time. The relatively short chronological span between these phases, as indicated by the dendrochronological results, occurring at the beginning of the 58th century BCE, suggests that this transition was not a gradual process but rather a relatively rapid development. Overall, the results from trench T9000 substantially enhance the understanding of Lin 3 by confirming multi-phase occupation, refining the ceramic sequence, and providing new evidence for domestic activities, architectural organization, and possible ritual or symbolic practices.

3.2 Underwater excavation fields 6 and 7 (2024)

The most remarkable discovery in 2023 was a triple-row palisade system (see fig. 14) from around 4500 BCE of densely set piles situated more than 150 metres further lakeward than the trenches examined in 2021. A fourth palisade runs perpendicular to this system.

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Fig. 11 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Complete flint blade from trench 9000 measuring approximately 25 cm (photo R. Ruka, Albanian Academy of Sciences, EXPLO project)

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Fig. 12 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
Trench 9000, West and North Profiles,
cultural layers 18–24 resp. 110–115,
sterile lake marl layers 26–28 resp. 116
(graphics A. Bieri, University of Bern,
EXPLO project)

One of the most significant findings of 2024 was the confirmation that this previously identified perpendicular row of piles represents an additional palisade phase, now securely dated to around 4000 BCE.

This discovery reinforces the interpretation of Lin 3 as a fortified settlement, with multiple construction phases indicating a complex and strategic approach to settlement defence (YERMOKHIN et al. 2025a). Finds of ceramic objects in the underwater trenches were relatively sparse, which supports the interpretation that the cultural layers in this area have been significantly impacted by erosion. However, the density of ceramic finds noticeably increased in those parts of the trenches situated closer to the shoreline. The underwater excavations of 2024 further confirmed that the settlement area extended beyond the originally assumed boundaries, covering at least six hectares, making Lin 3 one of the largest prehistoric sites in Albania.

3.3 Dendrochronology

Underwater and lakeshore excavations conducted over four seasons at Lin 3 uncovered more than 900 anthropogenic processed wooden elements from buildings and structures, mostly from juniper, oak, and pine (figs. 4 and 14). The dendrochronological results for the terrestrial part of the site dating to the early 6th millennium BCE are under preparation (YERMOKHIN et al. 2025b). In the archaeological area investigated under water in 2023 and 2024 large concentrations of wooden piles were documented (YERMOKHIN et al. 2025a). Using statistical programs (TSAP-Win, COFECHA, ARSTAN) and visual cross-dating techniques, we could construct a 192-year-long floating tree-ring chronology named LIN3-01. This sequence is based on 164 well-correlated pine samples, mostly collected from linear structures interpreted as palisades (fig. 13). Tree-ring width data were analysed

to detect synchronous growth patterns and identify missing rings, a common issue in trees growing under closed canopy conditions. Radiocarbon dating (via wiggle-matching of four samples) and dendrochronological cross-dating with regional chronologies anchored the LIN3-01 sequence to an end-date of 4347–4333 cal BCE, with a median value of 4340 BCE. This sequence fits precisely with previously established oak and juniper chronologies from the site of Ploča Mičov Grad across the lake in North Macedonia, extending the regional dendrochronological framework to 418 years (BOLLIGER, HAFNER & TINNER 2023; MACZKOWSKI, BOLLIGER & FRANCUZ 2025; REICH et al. 2025).

The analysis of tree felling dates revealed a detailed construction sequence spanning over six decades (fig. 14). Three successive palisades were built at the site, forming a defensive system at the lake side periphery of the settlement. The dating indications in the following section are averaged radiocarbon dates, modelled (“wiggle-matched”) by using the D_Sequence command in OxCal v.4.4 (BRONK RAMSEY, VAN DER PLICHT & WENINGER 2001; GALIMBERTI, RAMSEY & MANNING 2004; BRONK RAMSEY 2009) and compared to the atmospheric data from the IntCal20 calibration curve (REIMER et al. 2020) with curve resolution set at 1 year:

- First activity (4404 cal BCE): The earliest dated activity is represented by five piles with waney edge, possibly test constructions or temporary features.
- Palisade Ia (4386 cal BCE): Built 18 years later, this palisade consisted of 35 piles (in the trench), mostly from trees aged 60–110 years. The wood shows a high preservation rate, with nearly all samples retaining their final growth rings.
- Palisade Ib (4373 cal BCE): A minor repair or expansion of Palisade I occurred 13 years later, with six new piles inserted.
- Palisade IIa and IIb (4349 and 4344 cal BCE): Two segments of this palisade were constructed 37 and 42 years after Palisade Ia. The second segment shows evidence of early spring felling (based on partial earlywood).

Fig. 13 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania

LIN3-01 pine tree-ring chronology:

a: The orange line represents the raw tree-ring chronology in millimetres (left scale); the grey line is the number of series in each year (right scale); green rectangular boxes on the curves with attached numbers are positions and lab labels of ¹⁴C samples

b: Cross-dating of the raw pine tree-ring chronologies from Lin (LIN3-01), against Ploča Mičov Grad oak (MKO-100), and juniper (MKO-101) chronologies

c: End-date ranges for LIN3-01 chronology resulting from the wiggle matching of ¹⁴C dates: only from LIN3-01 chronology (left, four ¹⁴C dates), and from a combined model also including the ¹⁴C from Ploča chronologies (right, twenty ¹⁴C dates)¹

(graphics: from YERMOKHIN et al. 2025a)

¹ For OxCal CQL code, see supplementary material S2 available at <https://zenodo.org/uploads/14138187>, detailed data will be made available on request; OxCal 4.4 (BRONK RAMSEY, VAN DER PLICHT & WENINGER 2001; GALIMBERTI, RAMSEY & MANNING 2004; BRONK RAMSEY 2009; REIMER et al. 2020).

Fig. 14 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
 Triple-row palisade system of the mid-5th millennium BCE. A fourth palisade dated around 4000 BCE cuts this system perpendicular. Evolution of Palisades I–III.
 The LIN3-01 tree-ring chronology end-date is set at median modelled end-date of 4340 cal BCE. The first construction activities took place 64 years earlier, in 4404 cal BCE. All data in relative years calculated on the first felling date. Circle size indicates pile diameter (multiplied by two for visibility).
 a: Piles from year 1 (red)
 b: Piles from Palisade Ia, year 18 (purple), and repair Palisade Ib, year 31 (green)
 c: Piles from Palisade IIa, year 55 (orange), and Palisade IIb, year 60 (blue)
 d. Palisade III, year 64 (black, 4340 cal BCE)
 e. Cross-dated piles without a final ring or appeared in separate years
 f. All cross-dated samples
 (graphics: from YERMOKHIN et al. 2025a)

— Palisade III (4340 cal BCE): Built 4 years after Palisade IIb, this large palisade included 82 piles. Its proximity and connection to the earlier palisades suggest coordinated planning and maintenance over time.

The diameters and tree-ring numbers of the piles reveal differences in forest management and wood selection practices. Palisade I shows a continuous distribution of tree ages, characteristic of a primary forest. In contrast, Palisades IIb and III display bimodal age distributions, possibly indicating a mixed-use strategy or regrowth in previously harvested areas (YERMOKHIN et al. 2025a). The linear arrangement and repeated rebuilding of the palisades suggest they served an important role, likely as defensive structures. This is consistent with other Neolithic enclosures across Europe. Their maintenance over 64 years reflects long-term occupation and investment in communal infrastructure. The prevalence of pine, unusual for Neolithic lakeshore sites of Lake Ohrid where oak typically dominates, raises interesting ecological questions. Pine, a pioneer species, may have thrived in secondary growth areas following land clearance or fire. This aligns with the idea that earlier human activity had altered local forest dynamics, promoting pine regeneration. The strong correlation between tree-ring series from Lin 3 and those from Ploča Mičov Grad confirms that cross-species dendrochronology is viable in this region.

4. Conclusions and outlook

The 2024 excavations at Lin 3, encompassing both underwater and terrestrial investigations, have yielded major advances in our understanding of early Neolithic wetland habitation

of southern Europe. The new findings confirm that Lin 3 was a multi-phase settlement, intermittently occupied over nearly two millennia between 5900 and 3900 BCE (fig. 15). The presence of a well-organized defensive palisade system provides compelling evidence that early Neolithic communities in this region actively invested in settlement protection, challenging previous assumptions about early village life. The documentation of two distinct palisade construction phases, dated to 4400 and 4000 BCE, indicates that fortification was not a singular event but rather a recurrent and integral aspect of settlement planning. This suggests that defensive architecture was a standardized and sustained feature of Neolithic communities in this area, pointing to a broader regional pattern of long-term strategic investment in security and resilience. This finding aligns with broader regional patterns in which environmental or socio-economic factors may have prompted periodic abandonment and reoccupation. The use of wooden piles in all phases confirms Lin 3 as a pile-dwelling site adapted to fluctuating water levels. Key discoveries from trench T9000 in 2024, such as dense ceramics clusters, oven installations, and traces of burning on some piles, provide compelling evidence for complex domestic activities. Notable artefacts like an exceptional large flint blade, *Spondylus* beads, and anthropomorphic figurines, underscore the settlement's participation in local and potentially long-distance exchange networks. The exclusive presence of impressed ware in the lower settlement phase points to cultural or technological changes occurring over a relatively short period during the early 58th century BCE. Together, these insights refine the site's chronology, shed light on the inhabitants' adaptive strategies, and highlight the settlement's long-term importance for understanding Neolithic life in the region.

Looking ahead, the planned 2025 field season will focus on bridging the gap between trenches T6000 and T9000, offering a more continuous stratigraphic assessment. This will test whether observed occupational interruptions were localized or more general phenomena of the sites sequence and reveal how domestic structures, refuse zones, and other functional areas were organized. Targeted sampling strategies, including dendrochronological, radiocarbon, and bioarchaeological analyses, will further refine the settlement's timeline and clarify the nature of ceramic and technological shifts between occupation phases. Expanded bioarchaeological work including any additional human remains will shed light on diet, and probably health, within this early farming community. These findings confirm Lin 3's standing as one of the most significant early pile-dwelling

Fig. 15 Lin 3, Lake Ohrid, Albania
 Overview of the phases between 5800 and 3900 BCE defined by a combination of radiocarbon dating and dendrochronology (graphics M. Yermokhin, A. Maczkowski, University of Bern, EXPLO project)

settlements in Europe, challenging assumptions about the uniformity of Neolithic wetland communities by highlighting distinct construction phases, cultural transitions, and potential episodes of fire-related destruction.

Continued collaboration between Albania and Switzerland is essential not only for advancing research but also for supporting preservation efforts and fostering public engagement. These efforts will help ensure that the exceptional cultural heritage of Lin 3 remains accessible for future generations. Protecting this site is critical for safeguarding one of the most important windows into Neolithic wetland habitation in southeastern Europe. Lin 3 stands out as a rare and invaluable example of well-preserved Neolithic wooden architecture in the Balkans. The successful application of dendrochronological dating at the site highlights the extraordinary potential of submerged, waterlogged settlements for producing high-resolution environmental and archaeological data. By combining dendrochronology, radiocarbon dating, and meticulous stratigraphic excavation, Lin 3 serves as a key reference point for understanding Neolithic land use, forest management, and social organization in the region.

The exceptional chronological framework, the remarkable depth of occupation spanning over 2000 years, and the outstanding state of preservation make Lin 3 a perfect counterpart to the UNESCO World Heritage sites of the Alpine region (*“Prehistoric Pile Dwellings around the Alps”*). This clearly demonstrates that the prehistoric wetland sites of the Balkans are of equal importance and deserve corresponding recognition and protection.

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